

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE YOUTH LEARNING IN SOCIAL PARTNERSHIPS WITH EMPLOYERS

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Annotation: *The article discusses how social partnership in the sphere of labor is closely related to social partnership in the sphere of vocational education, which is understood as “interaction with the subjects of economic life and the sphere of labor in order to increase the effectiveness of vocational education and meet the demand for the skills and competencies of the labor force in the labor market”.*

Keywords: *trained specialist, candidates, social partners, education process*

The employer today needs not just a trained specialist, but a graduate who is ready to perform production tasks with high quality.

With regard to the system of vocational education, the severity of the problem of quality is expressed in the fact that there are contradictions between the quality of training specialists and the needs of modern production.

Consider, as an example, the data of the Research Center of the UzJob portal. In total there are 55 vacancies and 2854 resumes, 15 vacancies and 800 resumes for all of an inventory accountant. But only 60% of applicants have similar work experience. At the same time, 90% of vacancies contain experience requirements, which complicates the search for candidates. The supply / demand ratio in this case is 53.3 resumes per (accountant)vacancy.

Candidates with at least six months of experience in accounting can apply for the position of warehouse accountant. Candidates for this position should know the basics of accounting, tax legislation, and have the skills to work with the 1C: 8 program.

Employers are quite loyal to the education of applicants. Graduates of financial and economic colleges and universities, candidates with incomplete higher education can apply for entry-level positions. Social partnership is a system of interaction between an educational institution and consumers of personnel, state, public organizations, based on the identification, coordination and implementation of the interests of all participants in the agreement, these are relations built on mutual interest in the end result.

At the same time, the main goals of social partnership are:

- increasing the adequacy of the result of the educational activities of the college to public expectations, the needs of the individual, the sphere of work and specific employers through the harmonization and integration of the educational process in a general education school;

- staffing of the educational process;
- ensuring professional adaptation and social - professional socialization and self-realization of students and graduates;
- implementation of a competency-based approach in professional education.

The interaction of the college with social partners is carried out in various forms and directions, such as:

- improvement of the organization and content of the integral educational process;
- integration of the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard of secondary vocational education and professional standards;
- Strengthening the connection between student education and production;
- Constant study of the labor market, etc.

Work to create a mechanism for effective social partnership is a movement towards each other. In our college, it consists of the following stages: 1) Preparatory - at this stage, we have identified the main groups of social partners and areas for the development of partnerships, monitoring the need for personnel, forming a "portfolio of assumptions" to establish forms of cooperation. 2) Organizational - development of the regulatory framework interaction (conclusion of agreements), development of criteria for the effectiveness of social partnership, formation of organizational structures. 3) Backbone - improvement of the software and methodological support of the educational process based on the requirements of the field of activity, optimization of production practice, development of uniform criteria for the level of specialist competence, development of adaptation methods, employment of graduates. Social partnership allows for a flexible approach to the preparation of students, using a variable component of the educational program, including new disciplines or in-depth courses that meet the needs of the employer. Practice shows that key competencies are formed only through their own experience, so the educational environment should be built in such a way that the student finds himself in situations that contribute to their formation. Improving the quality of graduate training is impossible without the active help of customers - employers. The success of our student as a future specialist is largely formed during the internship, when theoretical knowledge is transformed into specific skills in maintaining a specific section of accounting or cash transactions with a specific client. The opportunity to see the concrete results of their work allows the student to realize the importance of the profession, to lay the foundation for future success. And here it is necessary to

observe the unity of requirements for the student, both on the part of college teachers and on the part of social partners.

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